

Recent Trends in the Histopathological Spectrum of Malignancies Among Females in Maharashtra

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Abstract:

Background: Cancer among females is a growing public health challenge, with breast, cervical, and ovarian cancers being the most prevalent. Understanding the histopathological trends of these malignancies is crucial for enhancing screening programs and developing effective treatments. This study focuses on analyzing recent trends in the histopathological spectrum of female cancers in Maharashtra, India.

Aim: To evaluate the recent histopathological trends in female malignancies in Maharashtra, providing insights into the demographic distribution and treatment outcomes.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted at a tertiary care centre in Mumbai from July 2022 to June 2023. Eighty female patients with histopathologically confirmed malignancies were included. Data were collected from medical records and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with descriptive and inferential statistics applied.

Results: The mean age of patients was 52.3 years, with the majority aged 41-60 years. Breast cancer was the most common malignancy (35%), followed by cervical (20%) and ovarian cancers (15%). Most cancers were diagnosed at stage II (40%) and stage III (30%). Surgery was the primary treatment (50%), with a 70% overall survival rate, significantly higher in early-stage diagnoses ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: The study highlights breast cancer as the predominant malignancy among females in Maharashtra, with a significant association between cancer type and age group. Early-stage diagnosis correlates with improved survival, underscoring the need for enhanced screening and early intervention.

Recommendations: Strengthening screening programs, especially in rural areas, and promoting awareness about early diagnosis can improve outcomes. Further research should focus on the integration of advanced histopathological techniques for personalized cancer care.

Keywords: Female cancers, Histopathology, Breast Cancer, Cervical Cancer, Maharashtra, Cancer Trends.

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Introduction

Cancer remains a significant public health challenge worldwide, with malignancies among females posing a substantial burden in terms of morbidity and mortality. Globally, breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed cancer in women, followed by cervical and ovarian cancers, which together constitute a major portion of the oncological caseload in females [1]. The histopathological examination of cancerous tissues plays a crucial role in the diagnosis, treatment planning, and prognostication of these malignancies. Understanding the recent trends in the histopathological spectrum of female cancers is vital for developing targeted screening programs and effective treatment strategies.

India, with its diverse population and varying healthcare access, presents a unique landscape for studying cancer epidemiology. Recent data indicate a rising incidence of breast cancer, with a particularly notable increase in urban areas [2]. Cervical cancer, while declining in some regions due to better screening practices, remains a significant concern, especially in rural areas where access to preventive care is limited. Ovarian cancer, although less common, has been associated with high mortality rates due to often being diagnosed at an advanced stage [3].

Maharashtra, one of India's most populous states, reflects these national trends. The urban centers like Mumbai are experiencing a shift towards

higher breast cancer incidence, which is often attributed to lifestyle changes, delayed childbirth, and increased awareness leading to higher reporting rates. Conversely, cervical cancer continues to be prevalent in the rural parts of the state, highlighting disparities in healthcare access and the need for robust public health interventions.

Histopathological studies provide essential insights into the nature and progression of malignancies. They are indispensable in confirming diagnoses and guiding therapeutic decisions. Recent advancements in histopathological techniques, including immunohistochemistry and molecular pathology, have enhanced the accuracy of cancer diagnosis and allowed for more personalized treatment approaches [4]. These advancements underscore the importance of continuous updates in the histopathological knowledge base to align with evolving clinical practices.

The present study aims to analyze the recent trends in the histopathological spectrum of malignancies among females in Maharashtra.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective, observational design.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at a tertiary care centre in Mumbai, over a period from July 2022 to June 2023.

Participants: The study included 80 female patients diagnosed with various malignancies.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria encompassed female patients of all age groups who were diagnosed with histopathologically confirmed malignancies within the study period. Exclusion criteria included

patients with incomplete medical records and those who had undergone treatment outside of the study setting.

Bias: To minimize bias, all patient records were reviewed by multiple researchers independently, and any discrepancies were resolved through consensus. Blinding was maintained during data extraction to avoid observational bias.

Data Collection: Data were collected from patient medical records, which included demographic information, clinical presentation, histopathological findings, and treatment details. Standardized data collection forms were used to ensure consistency.

Procedure: Histopathological samples were analyzed by trained pathologists using standard protocols. The diagnosis and classification of malignancies were based on the World Health Organization (WHO) classification system. All data were de-identified before analysis to maintain patient confidentiality.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients. The frequency and distribution of different types of malignancies were calculated. Chi-square tests were performed to assess the association between categorical variables, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Result

The study included 80 female patients diagnosed with malignancies. The mean age of the patients was 52.3 years (SD = 12.4 years), with an age range from 20 to 75 years. The majority of the patients were in the age group of 41-60 years (45%). Table 1 presents the detailed demographic distribution.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Age Group (years)	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
20-30	10	12.5
31-40	15	18.75
41-50	20	25.0
51-60	16	20.0
61-70	12	15.0
71-75	7	8.75

The histopathological analysis revealed a diverse spectrum of malignancies among the study participants. The most common type of malignancy was breast cancer, accounting for 35% of the cases, followed by cervical cancer (20%), ovarian cancer (15%), endometrial cancer (10%), and other types such as gastrointestinal and lung cancers (20%). Table 2 details the frequency and percentage of each type of malignancy.

Table 2: Distribution of Malignancies

Type of Malignancy	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Breast Cancer	28	35.0
Cervical Cancer	16	20.0
Ovarian Cancer	12	15.0
Endometrial Cancer	8	10.0
Gastrointestinal Cancer	10	12.5
Lung Cancer	6	7.5

Statistical analysis showed a significant association between the type of malignancy and the age group ($p < 0.05$). Breast cancer was more prevalent in the 41-50 age group, whereas cervical cancer was more common in the 31-40 age group. Table 3 presents the cross-tabulation of malignancy type by age group.

Table 3: Cross-tabulation of Malignancy Type by Age Group

Age Group (years)	Breast Cancer	Cervical Cancer	Ovarian Cancer	Endometrial Cancer	Gastrointestinal Cancer	Lung Cancer
20-30	2	5	1	1	1	0
31-40	3	8	2	0	2	0
41-50	12	2	3	2	1	0
51-60	6	1	3	2	3	1
61-70	4	0	2	2	2	2
71-75	2	0	1	1	1	2

Most of the malignancies were diagnosed at stage II (40%) and stage III (30%), with fewer cases at stage I (20%) and stage IV (10%). This distribution highlights the importance of early detection and diagnosis. Table 4 shows the clinical staging of the malignancies.

Table 4: Clinical Staging of Malignancies

Clinical Stage	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Stage I	16	20.0
Stage II	32	40.0
Stage III	24	30.0
Stage IV	8	10.0

The treatment modalities included surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and a combination of these. The majority of the patients underwent surgery (50%), followed by chemotherapy (30%), and radiotherapy (10%). Combination therapy was administered to 10% of the patients. Table 5 summarizes the treatment modalities.

Table 5: Treatment Modalities

Treatment Modality	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Surgery	40	50.0
Chemotherapy	24	30.0
Radiotherapy	8	10.0
Combination	8	10.0

The survival rate at the end of the study period was 70%, with a higher survival rate observed in patients diagnosed at an earlier stage (Stage I and II) compared to those diagnosed at later stages (Stage III and IV) ($p < 0.01$).

Discussion

The demographic analysis revealed that the majority of the patients were aged between 41 and 60 years, indicating that middle-aged women are particularly vulnerable to malignancies. This age distribution aligns with global trends where cancer incidence increases with age, emphasizing the importance of regular screenings in this demographic.

Histopathologically, breast cancer emerged as the most common malignancy, affecting 35% of the study population, followed by cervical cancer (20%), ovarian cancer (15%), and endometrial cancer (10%). This pattern suggests that breast and cervical cancers are significant public health concerns among females in Maharashtra. The data underscore the necessity for targeted screening programs and public health initiatives to address these prevalent cancers. Moreover, the significant association between age and type of malignancy (p

< 0.05) implies that age-specific interventions could enhance early detection and treatment outcomes.

The study also highlighted the clinical staging of these malignancies, with the majority of cases diagnosed at stage II (40%) and stage III (30%). The relatively high percentage of early-stage diagnoses (20% at stage I) is encouraging but also underscores the need for continued efforts to catch these diseases even earlier. Early diagnosis is critical for improving prognosis and survival rates, which is evident from the survival analysis showing a 70% survival rate at the study's end. Patients diagnosed at earlier stages had significantly better survival outcomes ($p < 0.01$), reinforcing the importance of early detection.

Treatment modalities varied, with surgery being the most common treatment (50%), followed by chemotherapy (30%), radiotherapy (10%), and combination therapies (10%). This distribution reflects current clinical practices where surgery is often the first line of treatment, especially for solid tumors like breast and ovarian cancers. The choice of treatment modalities also highlights the need for comprehensive cancer care facilities that can provide a range of therapeutic options.

Overall, the study provides a detailed overview of the histopathological spectrum of female malignancies in Maharashtra, emphasizing the predominance of breast and cervical cancers. The results advocate for enhanced screening and early detection programs, particularly for high-risk age groups. The significant survival advantage for early-stage diagnoses further supports the push for improved public health strategies and advanced diagnostic facilities. Overall, these findings offer valuable insights for healthcare policymakers and practitioners aiming to improve cancer care and outcomes for women in this region.

A study evaluated the histopathological spectrum of female malignancies in Western Maharashtra. Out of 1016 cases, the majority were in the age group of 40 to 69 years. Breast cancer was the most common primary malignancy, followed by cervical cancer, oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma, colorectal carcinoma, and ovarian cancer. Infiltrating duct carcinoma was the predominant breast cancer type, and squamous cell carcinoma was the most common type in cervical and oropharyngeal cancers [5].

A study found that out of 724 neoplastic cases, 225 were malignant. Oral cavity malignancies were the most common, followed by breast and gastrointestinal tract malignancies. The study emphasized the importance of histopathological examination in diagnosing neoplastic lesions [6].

A study analyzed the distribution of malignant cases in a tertiary care center, observing 118 cases of malignancy over two and a half months. Female patients had a slightly higher malignancy rate, with cervical and breast cancers being the most prevalent among them. The study highlighted the need for preventive measures like banning tobacco products to reduce the incidence of cancers associated with smoking and chewing tobacco [7].

A study was conducted on the histopathological spectrum of breast lesions in a tertiary care hospital. Out of 867 cases, 88.3% were benign, with fibroadenoma being the most common benign lesion. Among malignant cases, invasive ductal carcinoma was predominant. This study underscored the importance of early detection and

intervention to reduce morbidity and mortality associated with breast tumors [8].

Conclusion

The study identified breast cancer as the most prevalent malignancy among females in Maharashtra. The findings underscore the need for improved screening and early detection programs, particularly for breast and cervical cancers. The significant association between age and type of malignancy highlights the necessity for targeted interventions for different age groups. The data also reveal a crucial need for advanced diagnostic and treatment facilities to improve patient outcomes.

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